

REFORMS IN THE SYSTEM OF MILITARY TRAINING IN UZBEKISTAN DURING THE YEARS OF INDEPENDENCE

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Abstract: *This article provides information on the reforms implemented in the system of military training in Uzbekistan during the years of independence. The article also mentions the decisions taken by the President to reform the military personnel system.*

Keywords: *Independence, state, military personnel, reform, development, law, training, system, service, education, professional.*

It is gratifying to note that over the past thirty years, Uzbekistan has come a long way. In a historically short period of time, our country has earned a worthy place in the world community.

Today, under the leadership of the head of our state, we are building a new Uzbekistan based on democratic and democratic principles. To this end, the most important task is to strengthen peace and stability, which are our priceless treasures.

The law enforcement agencies of the new Uzbekistan are also being renewed and improved. In his congratulatory message on the occasion of his professional holiday last year, the President said: had confessed. This appreciation encourages peacekeepers to work even harder to uphold the rule of law.

It should be noted that a number of sectoral services of the Ministry have been radically reformed. The work of law enforcement agencies in the fight against crime, its prevention, maintaining public order, ensuring the safety of citizens, raising the legal culture of the population has been radically improved.

2017 as a logical continuation of the reforms in the system. On November 29, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan adopted a resolution "On measures to radically improve the procedure for working with personnel in law enforcement agencies and the organization of their services." An important aspect of this decision is that it served as a basis for the consolidation of mechanisms for the organization of service in the police.

In order to ensure the implementation of this document, measures are being taken to increase the personal responsibility of law enforcement officials at all levels for the selection of business and professional personnel, their targeted placement and unconditional performance of their duties. Particular attention was paid, first of all, to the formation of a promising management structure, as well as the recruitment of personnel who know the vacancies well and work quickly, taking into account the tasks and functions assigned to them. In order to ensure the transparency of the admission system to the law enforcement agencies, systematic advocacy work has been intensified in each law enforcement agency to fill the vacancies.

Specific tasks have been set for the formation of a permanent staff of law enforcement agencies, incentives to extend the service life of employees, as well as the proper distribution of personnel, taking into account their professional qualifications and personal abilities. . As a result, additional conditions have been created for law enforcement officers to serve.

The Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated August 16, 2017 "On measures to radically improve the system of training, retraining and advanced training of law enforcement officers" was the basis for the creation of a completely new system. This decision serves to educate the younger generation as mature professionals, to teach them the secrets of modern science and technology, to ensure that they grow up to be selfless people for the welfare of the country and the peace of the people.

Speaking about the Academy of the Ministry of Internal Affairs, the head of state stressed that this university should become a prestigious educational institution for law enforcement agencies to study, analyze, evaluate and implement the experience gained in the field of training in our country and abroad. had confessed. Today, the Academy successfully fulfills such important tasks as training law enforcement officers, loyal servants of the Motherland and the people, conducting in-depth scientific research in the field of law, development of draft regulations on the basis of advanced pedagogical technologies. is doing.

At present, the Academy pays special attention to strengthening cooperation with the fight against crime in the training of students and cadets. To this end, trainees and cadets are undergoing internships in the sectoral services of law enforcement agencies, and the departments of specialization are staffed with academic degrees and extensive practical experience.

A unique system of training has been created. On this basis, 14 departmental academic lyceums, the Temurbek School and a specialized boarding school have been established to form a core of staff. The Academy of the Ministry offers full-time and part-time study in 8 areas. The Institute of Advanced Training of the Ministry of Internal Affairs is functioning.

Of course, the successful completion of the tasks ahead of us requires us to increase the level of professional knowledge of all personnel serving in the system. After all, "It is our highest duty to faithfully serve the Motherland and the people!" Only an employee who has the noble idea in his heart and mind will do his job sincerely. To achieve this, we need to organize spiritual and educational work in a completely new way.

The first is the formation of highly qualified personnel. A person of high spirituality is distinguished by such noble qualities as selflessness, courage, bravery, tolerance, love for the Motherland, respect for our national values, and pride in our great ancestors.

Second, to train patriotic, loyal cadres. True patriotism means living in the interests of the nation, the Motherland, working and fighting for its future. A patriot is with his people in good and bad days, he seeks his happiness in the happiness of the Motherland.

Third, to develop a culture of reading in the training of knowledgeable and potential personnel. It is important to improve the culture of reading in the training of highly qualified personnel. The book plays an important role in educating law enforcement officers in the spirit of high professional culture, respect for national and universal values, love for the Fatherland and devotion to the ideas of independence.

Fourth, to accelerate educational work with staff. Therefore, special attention is paid to the training of personnel in law enforcement agencies, the further improvement of this system. Appropriate work is being done to further improve the existing education system. In particular, a number of positive steps are being taken to educate young employees in the spirit of love for the motherland, dedication to the profession, strengthening service discipline and legitimacy.

Fifth, strengthen employee social protection measures. To this end, the issues of housing, subsidies, and payment of rent for long-term employees of the law enforcement agencies and their families are being addressed. The Ministry of Internal Affairs and the local authorities are conducting a list of people in need of housing and providing them with service accommodation. In short, sharing the joys and sorrows of employees has become a constant work, a spiritual need.

In the system of law enforcement agencies, sufficient conditions have been created for the professional development of personnel, continuous improvement of combat and physical training. The ministry has a state-of-the-art training center that includes a gym, hand-to-hand combat room, gyms, a shooting range, a service training room and a test center.

Training is under way for senior officers to be promoted to major, lieutenant colonel and colonel. Classes are held in the form of lectures, talks, seminars, practical methods. Curricula, manuals, textbooks are developed by the relevant services and regularly delivered to the staff during the training. Employees' knowledge is tested through tests and oral interviews, shooting exercises in combat training, and physical fitness tests.

In addition, in order to increase the combat readiness, theoretical knowledge and practical skills of officers in law enforcement agencies and systems, the personnel are provided with the requirements of the normative documents of the Ministry of Internal Affairs in the field of service.

Practical shooting exercises are being held with the personnel of the Central Office and subsystems of the Ministry of Internal Affairs. In addition, the staff is trained in hand-to-hand combat and sambo by experienced instructors.

Sports competitions and contests are held to improve the professional skills and combat readiness of service personnel. In particular, the republican competitions in all-around, football, mini-football, hand-to-hand combat, volleyball, athletics, badminton, table tennis, chess and other sports are held. As a result, it is gratifying that our athletes are defending the honor of our country in the international arena and achieving high results.

Spiritual and educational reforms in our country are considered as one of the priorities of state policy. Many measures are being taken in our country to further improve the spiritual and educational environment, to promote our centuries-old traditions and values.

As in all spheres, the law enforcement agencies need to raise the level of spiritual and educational work among the personnel to a qualitatively new level, to further increase the level of knowledge of employees, to develop highly moral, patriotic, loyal and dedicated employees. special attention is paid to the formation.

Resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 2, 2021 "On additional organizational measures to further improve the activities of law enforcement agencies in the field of public safety and the fight against crime" The concept of organization of educational work "was approved. In this concept, it is important to further improve the system of

effective organization of spiritual and educational work in law enforcement agencies, to strengthen the moral potential and ideological immunity of employees, to strengthen in their minds a sense of belonging to the fate and future of the Motherland. 'goals are reflected.

In conclusion, I would like to emphasize that the fight against any crime requires a great deal of responsibility from the staff to ensure the peace of citizens and the rule of law in the country. Only courageous, patriotic, self-sacrificing, loyal and honest employees can fulfill these responsibilities. The concept states that the main requirements for law enforcement officers are to adhere to a culture of treatment, to listen carefully to the applicant, to set a personal example by approaching the situation objectively and conscientiously.

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